

STORIES FROM THE REGION: PRAGMATIC DIGITAL PRESERVATION

Joshua TJ Ng

*Te Rua Mahara o te
Kāwanatanga
Archives New Zealand
New Zealand
Joshua.Ng@dia.govt.nz
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7523-2031>*

Asti Sherring

*National Museum of
Australia
Australia
Asti.Sherring@nma.gov.au
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3376-5918>*

Karen Chan

*Asian Film Archive
Singapore
karen@asianfilmarchive.org*

Elijah Olawale Azeez

*National Library of Nigeria
Nigeria
azezelijaholawale@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9896-5207>*

Tim Kong

*National Library of New
Zealand
New Zealand
Tim.Kong@dia.govt.nz*

Kari James

*Pacific Manuscripts Bureau
(PAMBU)
Australia
kari.james@anu.edu.au*

Mengchun Tsai

*Freelance Audiovisual
Archivist
Taiwan
mpcbtsai@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4332-4290>*

Martino Cipriani

*RMIT University Vietnam
Vietnam
martinocipriani@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-5140-3250>*

Sanchai

Chotirosseranee
*Thai Film Archive (Public
Organization)
Thailand
thaiifilmarchive@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6625-1033>*

Abstract – This panel brings together digital preservation practitioners from the Southeast Asia-Pacific region and beyond to share pragmatic case studies grounded in local contexts. It will explore barriers to access, questions of knowledge and agency,^A and opportunities for regional collaboration—positioning the region’s voice in the global preservation conversation.

Submission Type – Panel Discussion

Keywords – community, local contexts, collaboration, pragmatism, regional identity

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey, and Tūhono - Connect.

I. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Digital preservation in the Southeast Asia-Pacific region is shaped by resourcefulness, collaboration, and cultural care. It is also shaped by barriers—both within institutions and across national and linguistic boundaries—and by a recognition that digital preservation practices, as currently defined by dominant frameworks, often reflect prevailing models of practice developed in different institutional and cultural contexts.

This panel brings together practitioners and advocates from Southeast Asia-Pacific region and beyond to share pragmatic digital preservation stories grounded in local realities. Each panellist will present a short case study reflecting how they are navigating limited resources, institutional blockers, and shifting understandings of what “best practice” looks like from where they stand.

Beyond sharing how digital preservation is being done, this panel asks:

- Who gets to define “good” or “best” practice?
- How can we centre digital preservation practices for *our* region?
- What happens when access is restricted—by cost, policy, or power?
- How do we move from technical compliance to cultural relevance?

Themes include digital preservation as a form of activism against erasure, gaps in access and digital agency, collaboration across borders and disciplines, and the importance of stepping outside one’s own context to share authority and reframe knowledge. The discussion will also spotlight common regional blockers—such as the conflation of digitisation and digital preservation, language barriers, and the steep costs of tools, infrastructure, and training.

Informed by the iPRES Regional Impact Committee’s discussions and SEAPAVAA community insights, this session not only celebrates what’s working but calls for deeper conversations about ethics, equity, and regional collaboration in digital preservation.

II. PROGRAM

Opening Provocation: 10 mins – set tone, frame big questions

Panelist Lightning Talks: 30 mins – practical stories, varied voices

Moderated Roundtable Discussion: 35 mins – deeper exploration of barriers, ethics, regional framing

Audience Q&A: 15 mins – open space for feedback, dialogue, action

III. PANELLISTS

Moderator: Joshua TJ Ng is Digital Preservation Analyst, Archives New Zealand. His work focuses on audiovisual preservation as well as the infrastructure

and processes supporting the Government Digital Archive (GDA).

Asti Sherring (she/her) Manager Changeable and Digital Collections, National Museum of Australia. She specialises in Time-based Media conservation and relational approaches to cultural heritage collections. Asti is currently undertaking doctorate research at the University of Canberra and is Honorary Senior Lecturer, Humanities, Arts and Social Science, Australian National University.

Karen Chan is the Executive Director of the Asian Film Archive (AFA). She is in her second term as President of Southeast Asia-Pacific Audiovisual Archive Association (SEAPAVAA) and is the current Chair of the Co-ordinating Council of Audiovisual Archives Associations (CCAAA).

Sanchai Chotirosseranee is the Deputy Director of the Thai Film Archive (Public Organization). He is on the executive committee of the Southeast Asia-Pacific Audiovisual Archive Association (SEAPAVAA) and the International Federation of Film Archives (FIAP).

Martino Cipriani is a Film and Digital Video Lecturer at RMIT University Vietnam and a PhD candidate at the University of Amsterdam. His research focuses on film heritage, digitization, media archaeology, and cultural conservation, underscoring his commitment to preserving and enhancing the circulation of Asian audiovisual culture.

Tim Kong is a citizen of Aotearoa New Zealand, with familial links to Fiji, China, and Scotland. He was raised in South-East Asia, living and being educated in Thailand, Malaysia and the Philippines. In 2020 he joined the National Library of New Zealand as the Programme Manager for the Pacific Virtual Museum project, and in 2022 became the Director, Digital Experience.

Kerrie Shaw holds a Diploma in Library and Information Studies, an Adv Dip in Local, Family and Applied History and a Grad Cert in Cultural Management. Kerrie is an experienced digitiser and practitioner of digital preservation and enjoys sharing her knowledge in this field and the other skills she has obtained over her career.

Kari James is the Executive Officer of the Pacific Manuscripts Bureau at the Australian National University. In this capacity, she serves on the Board of the ANU Pacific Institute and the Bureau of the

Pacific and Regional Branch of the International Council on Archives (PARBICA).

Mengchun Tsai is a freelance audiovisual archivist, formerly a technician and Head of the Film Restoration Team at TFAI. Responsible for film digitization, digital restoration, and the development of digital preservation infrastructure.

Elijah Olawale Azeez is a digital librarian at the National Library of Nigeria. He specializes in digital preservation, indigenous knowledge systems, and AI ethics.

IV. CONCLUSION

This session highlighted pragmatic practices, shared barriers, and collaboration opportunities, amplifying Southeast Asia-Pacific voices and advancing lasting regional impact through shared knowledge and agency.

DISCLOSURE

ChatGPT Plus has been used in editing and grammar enhancements in the preparation for this proposal.

